

SEMI-SUPERVISED TRANSFORMER-BASED CERVICAL SEGMENTATION: FUGC 2025 CHALLENGE

M. Islam^{1,*}, M. Tabassum^{1,*}, M. Elbatel², A. Mayr¹, C. Kremser¹, M. Haltmeier³, E. Almar-Munoz¹

¹ Department of Radiology, Medical University of Innsbruck, Innsbruck, Austria

² Department of Electronic and Computer Engineering, The Hong Kong University of Science and Technology, Hong Kong SAR, China

³ Department of Applied Mathematics, University of Innsbruck, Innsbruck, Austria

ABSTRACT

Semi Supervised Learning (SSL) is an effective solution for segmentation tasks in ultrasound images. In this paper, we have applied a transformer-based Semi-Supervised Segmentation model UniMatch V2, which is an upgraded version of the widely popular UniMatch. We implemented this model while participating in the Fetal Ultrasound Grand Challenge 2025. Our approach uses a ViT-based encoder (DINOv2) and utilizes weak-to-strong augmentation as its core for the semi-supervised pipeline. This approach achieved Dice Scores of 92.5% and 85.3% in the validation and test phases, respectively. Similarly, the Hausdorff Distances obtained were 21.19 and 62.29 for validation and test phases. As for now, we rank first in Hausdorff Distance and inference time and second in Dice Score, though the competition is ongoing.

Index Terms— Fetal Ultrasound, Semantic Segmentation, Weak-to-Strong Consistency, Vision Transformer.

1. INTRODUCTION

Ultrasound imaging is the standard imaging protocol to examine pregnant patients, and transvaginal ultrasound is the go-to method to monitor the cervix region as it provides a detailed impression of the cervical anatomy [1]. Accurate segmentation of cervical regions offers valuable information for treatment monitoring; however, manual annotation of ultrasound images is tedious and labor intensive, given the numerous frames in a single video. Studies show that Semi-Supervised Learning (SSL) in ultrasound imaging segmentation provides high segmentation accuracy by effectively utilizing unlabeled data [2]. SSL proves to be highly effective when labeled data is scarce, bridging the gap between limited annotations and robust model performance. However, robust and precise semi-supervised segmentation techniques remain limited, as most earlier-generation Semi-Supervised Segmentation (SSS) methods rely on ResNet-based encoders, which are suboptimal and insufficient for extracting high-quality features. Con-

sequently, UniMatch V2 [3] has adopted more advanced ViT-based encoders (e.g., DINOv2 [4]), which benefit from significantly larger-scale pre-training compared to their predecessors.

This paper presents our approach, which implements an enhanced version of UniMatch. Its core is built on weak-to-strong consistency regularization while integrating feature-level dropout and input-level augmentation within a single stream, making it more streamlined than the previous version. Furthermore, we implemented the FixMatch baseline [5] from the original paper and conducted a comparative analysis with our approach.

2. DATASET

We mainly used the transvaginal fetal ultrasound dataset provided by the challenge. The training set consists of 50 labeled 2D ultrasound images and 450 unlabeled images. The validation (90 samples) and test (300 samples) sets are hidden. All images were size 544×336 pixels and encoded as 8-bit images. The mask consisted of three classes: Background, Anterior Lip, and Posterior Lip.

Given the limited availability of unhidden ground truth masks, we reserved the last 10 images for internal validation. To prevent data leakage, we selected consecutive cases, as they may originate from the same video. This ensures that frames from the same video are not used for both training and validation.

We also incorporated an external dataset from the **Public Symphysis-Fetal Head Segmentation (PSFHS) Challenge** [6]. Specifically, we selected images of the cervix region and integrated them into our unlabeled dataset. This external dataset consisted of a total of 800 images.

3. METHODS

We primarily implemented two distinct Semi-Supervised Segmentation models for the challenge: **UniMatch V2** [3]

* The authors contributed equally.

and **FixMatch** [5]. Throughout the implementation, we explored various strategies, including different loss functions, varying sizes of DINOv2 encoders, and training with an external dataset. The following subsections provide a detailed discussion of these aspects.

3.1. Pre-processing

We focused on resizing the image dataset by dividing images into smaller patches before feeding them into the DINOv2 encoder. The original 544×336 images were resized to 560×336, allowing for an even division into patches. We experimented with interpolation and zero-padding, ultimately selecting zero-padding for its superior performance. Additionally, our methodology incorporated both weak and strong augmentation pipelines for semi-supervised training.

3.2. SSL Strategies

UniMatch V2 was the primary SSL strategy used in the competition. We also implemented FixMatch, which shares the same model architecture but differs in training. Both methods use the DPT (Dense Prediction Transformer [7]) framework with a DINOv2-based vision transformer for multi-level feature extraction and a multi-scale feature fusion head for dense prediction, integrating global contextual understanding with spatial refinement.

The key distinction lies in their augmentation strategies. FixMatch relies solely on input-space augmentations, whereas UniMatch V2 enhances representation learning by incorporating feature-level augmentations through Complementary Dropout, enabling dual-stream learning in a unified pipeline. This expands the augmentation space and improves segmentation performance, particularly when utilizing advanced vision foundation models like DINOv2.

We explored two loss functions during training:

- **Dice Loss**, a region-based loss that minimizes overlap error between predicted and ground truth masks, making it effective for handling class imbalance:

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{Dice}} = 1 - \frac{2 \sum y_i \hat{y}_i + \epsilon}{\sum y_i + \sum \hat{y}_i + \epsilon} \quad (1)$$

where y_i and \hat{y}_i represent the ground truth and predicted values, respectively, and ϵ prevents division by zero.

- **Cross-Entropy Loss**, a widely used classification loss that measures the discrepancy between predicted probabilities and ground truth labels:

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{CE}} = - \sum y_i \log(\hat{y}_i) \quad (2)$$

where y_i is the true class label and \hat{y}_i is the predicted probability.

For our experiments, we used two versions of the DINOv2 encoder: **small** and **base**. These differ in embedding dimensions, attention heads, and feature extraction capabilities, influencing the model’s ability to capture multi-scale information.

Encoder	Embed Dim	Depth	Heads	MLP	Out Ch.
Small	384	12	6	4	[48, 96, 192, 384]
Base	768	12	12	4	[96, 192, 384, 768]

Table 1: Comparison of DINOv2 Vision Transformer Encoder Variants.

We primarily employed two different training approaches. Initially, we fine-tuned the model using the dataset provided by the challenge. Subsequently, we expanded the unlabeled training set by incorporating cervix images from the PSFHS Challenge, which may improve performance.

4. TRAINING

The models were trained using an NVIDIA L4 GPU and an NVIDIA T4 GPU, with a fixed batch size 4. We employed the AdamW optimizer with an initial learning rate of $5e - 6$. Training was conducted for 60 epochs using the optimal configuration.

5. RESULTS

5.1. Segmentation Results on Internal Validation Set

Figures 1 and 2 provide a comparative analysis of FixMatch and UniMatch V2 for segmentation on our internal validation set.

Figure 1 highlights the segmentation predictions against the ground truth, where UniMatch V2 demonstrates better alignment, reducing false positives (red) and false negatives (green), while FixMatch exhibits more errors, particularly in anterior-posterior misclassification (yellow).

Figure 2 illustrates the Dice Score distribution, showing that UniMatch V2 maintains a more consistent performance with a higher median Dice Score, especially for the Posterior Lip (PL), whereas FixMatch displays a broader spread, indicating greater variability in segmentation accuracy.

5.2. Segmentation Results on Challenge Validation Set

Table 2 compares FixMatch and UniMatch V2 models with different DINO encoders in terms of Dice Score, Hausdorff Distance, and inference time. UniMatch V2 with DINO Base achieves the highest DSC (0.925) and lowest HD (21.19) compared to its baseline, FixMatch.

Model	Configuration	Segmentation Class	DSC	HD	Time (s)
FixMatch	DINO Small	Average	0.867 (± 0.060)	41.27 (± 27.33)	33.31
		Anterior Lip (AL)	0.862 (± 0.076)	44.94 (± 29.87)	
		Posterior Lip (PL)	0.871 (± 0.039)	37.58 (± 24.12)	
	DINO Small + Ex. D	Average	0.845 (± 0.073)	41.22 (± 25.95)	53.48
		Anterior Lip (AL)	0.883 (± 0.069)	34.74 (± 29.25)	
		Posterior Lip (PL)	0.808 (± 0.055)	47.70 (± 20.35)	
UniMatch V2	DINO Small	Average	0.912 (± 0.035)	26.22 (± 22.23)	56.25
		Anterior Lip (AL)	0.922 (± 0.035)	20.42 (± 20.75)	
		Posterior Lip (PL)	0.902 (± 0.036)	32.03 (± 25.89)	
	DINO Small + Ex. D	Average	0.879 (± 0.046)	34.49 (± 23.87)	60.95
		Anterior Lip (AL)	0.895 (± 0.051)	28.60 (± 25.12)	
		Posterior Lip (PL)	0.863 (± 0.041)	40.36 (± 27.98)	
	DINO Base	Average	0.925 (± 0.025)	21.19 (± 15.79)	152.63
		Anterior Lip (AL)	0.936 (± 0.020)	18.92 (± 17.13)	
		Posterior Lip (PL)	0.913 (± 0.030)	24.20 (± 20.30)	
	DINO Base + Ex. D	Average	0.911 (± 0.029)	25.95 (± 18.31)	155.54
		Anterior Lip (AL)	0.933 (± 0.022)	22.35 (± 19.42)	
		Posterior Lip (PL)	0.889 (± 0.034)	29.55 (± 22.68)	

Table 2: Performance metrics for FixMatch and UniMatch V2 with different configurations. Ex. D: External Dataset, DSC: Dice Similarity Coefficient, HD: Hausdorff Distance, and Time in seconds. The best results are highlighted in bold.

Fig. 1: Comparison of segmentation results between UniMatchV2 and FixMatch. Ground truth (GT) masks are displayed alongside the predicted outputs. The last row visualizes the error, where red indicates false positives, green represents false negatives, yellow highlights the anterior lip misclassified as posterior, and cyan marks the posterior lip misclassified as anterior.

Fig. 2: Boxplot comparison of Dice Scores across different SSL strategies on the internal validation set.

5.3. Segmentation Results on Challenge Test Set

Table 3 summarizes UniMatch V2’s test set performance with different DINO variants. The Base model achieved the highest DSC (0.863) and lowest HD (53.983) in 509 s.

Configuration	Class	DSC	HD	Time (s)
DINO Base	Average	0.863 (± 0.124)	53.983 (± 39.02)	509
	Anterior Lip (AL)	0.908 (± 0.068)	38.47 (± 26.92)	
	Posterior Lip (PL)	0.818 (± 0.149)	69.49 (± 42.93)	
DINO Base + Ex. D	Average	0.849 (± 0.128)	68.08 (± 50.82)	283
	Anterior Lip (AL)	0.894 (± 0.075)	54.27 (± 38.79)	
	Posterior Lip (PL)	0.806 (± 0.151)	81.89 (± 57.32)	
DINO Small	Average	0.839 (± 0.126)	62.29 (± 42.30)	104
	Anterior Lip (AL)	0.883 (± 0.078)	46.11 (± 38.79)	
	Posterior Lip (PL)	0.796 (± 0.159)	78.48 (± 51.12)	
DINO Small + Ex. D	Average	0.853 (± 0.099)	61.57 (± 44.97)	108
	Anterior Lip (AL)	0.891 (± 0.062)	47.30 (± 31.83)	
	Posterior Lip (PL)	0.814 (± 0.114)	75.84 (± 51.28)	

Table 3: Performance metrics for the best configurations on the test set. Ex. D: External Dataset, DSC: Dice Similarity Coefficient, HD: Hausdorff Distance, and Time in seconds. The best results are highlighted in bold.

6. DISCUSSION

Our findings demonstrate that UniMatch V2 consistently achieved excellent results on both the validation and test sets of the Challenge phase. Compared to the baseline FixMatch, its performance was consistently superior. While initial training strategies using only the challenge dataset exhibited strong performance on the validation set, they struggled on the test set, which contained significantly more images and potentially more challenging cases. To address this, incorporating an external dataset to expand the pool of unlabeled images proved highly effective. Although it led to a decrease in performance on the external validation set, it improved results on the test set, suggesting that the model was able to learn greater variability and generalize more effectively.

The resizing strategy was important in our approach. Initially, we used interpolation for padding images and masks, but switching to zero-padding led to better performance. Given that inference time was an important evaluation criterion in the challenge, we focused on training only base and small versions of the DINOv2 encoder. Switching from the base model to a small model improved both the Dice and Hausdorff Distance, resulting in a significantly higher inference time.

After experimenting with different loss functions, we selected cross-entropy loss as the optimal choice. Alternative loss functions were ineffective, as training became unstable when we replaced cross-entropy loss with Dice loss.

Despite achieving promising results, some limitations remained. The most notable challenge was improving segmentation performance for the posterior lip class. Various strategies, including adjusting the loss function to prioritize this class, were tested but ultimately deteriorated performance. We hypothesize that this issue stems from the limited availability of labeled training data and the inherent noise in ultrasound images, particularly due to the proximity of the posterior lip region to ultrasound artifacts.

7. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, our study highlights the effectiveness of UniMatch V2 for SSS in cervical region segmentation from transvaginal ultrasound. By leveraging DINOv2 encoders and weak-to-strong augmentation, UniMatch V2 outperformed FixMatch. Expanding the unlabeled dataset improved generalization, while zero-padding and cross-entropy loss contributed to stable training. Although posterior lip segmentation remained challenging, our approach proved robust and competitive. As of now, we rank first in Hausdorff Distance and inference time and second in Dice Score on the final test set leaderboard, though the competition is still ongoing.

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